

Assigning RUI Data to Multiple Tissue Blocks

Reusing RUI Locations

Author(s): Andreas Bueckle

Approved by: Katy Börner (May 20, 2022)

HIVE MC-IU Team, Indiana University

PI: Katy Börner

NIH Award No: 1OT2OD026671

Updated: April 26, 2022

Introduction

The long term goal of the HuBMAP consortium is to develop a reference atlas for the healthy human body at the single cell level. An important element of building this human atlas is defining a common coordinate system that can be used to locate data within the human body. The Indiana Mapping Component of HuBMAP has developed a system for locating samples within the human body based on a common coordinate system. This interface is referred to as the Registration User Interface (RUI).

The amount of data required to build a representative healthy human reference is astronomical. One important strategy for building this storehouse of data is to include data generated by other projects. Spatial registration of this data is critical. This SOP outlines using the RUI to identify the locations of standard sampling sites. This simplifies the tissue registration process since hundreds of samples can then inherit the same location

The procedures presented here have been used to assign spatial locations to data generated by the GTEx consortium, the Kidney Precision Medicine Project, SPARC, and the Human Cell Atlas.

Roles and Responsibilities

The **Subject Matter Expert (SME)** provides information (text, figures) for well-defined extraction site locations that are used to sample tissue data consistently across donors. Reviews and holds final responsibility for ensuring the correct assignment of tissue blocks to RUI locations.

The **Facilitator** is an MC-IU member who works with the SME to capture [RUI](#) data for extraction sites and then upload them to [Google Drive](#).

The **Systems Architect** assigns RUI data to tissue blocks

The **Principal Investigator (PI)** holds final responsibility for ensuring that accurate RUI locations are collected.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
SME	Varies by project	
Facilitator	Andreas Bueckle	abueckle@iu.edu
CNS Systems Architect	Bruce W. Herr II	bherr@indiana.edu
Principal Investigator	Katy Börner	katy@indiana.edu

Procedures

1. Initial contact between the SME and MC-IU is established either by the PI or the Facilitator.
2. The Facilitator points the SME to the most up-to-date [SOP](#) for Using the Registration User Interface, which includes a video demo.
3. The Facilitator then asks the SME to generate JSON files for all extraction sites.
4. If needed, the Facilitator and the SME meet on Zoom to register the desired extraction sites together.
5. Registering an extraction site works exactly like registering a tissue block via the RUI as outlined in the [SOP](#) for Using the Registration User Interface.
6. The resulting JSON file is then placed by the Facilitator into an appropriately named subfolder inside this Google Drive folder (<https://drive.google.com/drive/u/0/folders/1RUAwuc-S5hRSkTqMuqHUzF338CxrjRC>), and shared with the CNS Systems Architect.
7. The CNS Systems Architect, together with the Facilitator if needed, generates a JSON-LD file that can then be used to add non-HuBMAP entries to the Exploration User Interface (EUI). A sample JSON-LD file can be found here: https://github.com/hubmapconsortium/ccf-ui/blob/main/projects/ccf-eui/src/assets/gtex/data/rui_locations.jsonld
8. In order to facilitate this, the SME provides the Facilitator with a URL which links to the RUI location. This needs to be added to the link field of the sample list of objects in the `rui_locations.jsonld` file linked above.
9. The CNS Systems Architect then adds all relevant code changes to the EUI and creates a new production build.

References and Definitions

The below references and definitions were used in writing this Standard Operating Procedure. When available, definitions were taken from the [HuBMAP Dictionary](#), and aligned with standard terminologies used in relevant fields.

References

- The public Common Coordinate Framework Registration User Interface (CCF RUI): <https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf-ui/rui>. Accessed on Feb 20, 2021.
- HuBMAP Ingest Portal: <https://ingest.hubmapconsortium.org>.
- The CCF Portal: <https://hubmapconsortium.github.io/ccf>. Accessed on Feb 20, 2021.

Glossary

Common Coordinate Framework: see [HuBMAP Glossary](#).

HuBMAP: The Human BioMolecular Atlas Program is a consortium composed of diverse research teams funded by the [Common Fund at the National Institutes of Health](#). HuBMAP is developing the tools to create an open, global atlas of the human body at the cellular level. These tools and maps will be openly available, to accelerate understanding of the relationships between cell and tissue organization and function and human health.

Human Reference Atlas (HRA): The HRA is a comprehensive, high-resolution, three-dimensional atlas of all the cells in the healthy human body. The HRA provides standard terminologies and data structures for describing specimens, biological structures, and spatial positions linked to existing ontologies.

Registration User Interface (RUI): see [HuBMAP Glossary](#).

Subject Matter Expert (SME): An SME is a person with extensive knowledge about a given topic. In our case, SMEs lend us their expertise to ensure that RUI locations are registered in an anatomically correct manner.

Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs): SOPs are issued to specifically instruct team members in areas of responsibility, procedural steps, appropriate specifications and required records. SOPs outline procedures, which must be followed to support the reproducibility of scientific research. Procedures can take the form of a narrative, a flow chart, a process map, computer screen printouts or combination of all or any other suitable form, however must be written in appropriate, effective grammatical style. (e.g. plain English).

HuBMAP

Tissue Block: A tissue block is a digital, 3D representation of a tissue sample. In the RUI, tissue blocks are cuboids that the user can spatially register to a reference organ.